

IMPROVEMENT OF IMPREGNATION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CFRTP COMPOSITES BY MICRO-BRAIDED YARNS

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1 Introduction

The fabrication of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite involves two problems. The first one is that thermoplastics as matrices generally have high melt viscosity so that it is difficult to impregnate resin into reinforcing fiber bundle. To overcome this problem, micro-braided yarn (MBY) with CF and thermoplastic fiber have been developed as an intermediate material by Japanese traditional braiding technique as shown in Fig. 1. MBY is fabricated by braiding resin fibers alongside reinforcement fiber. Since resin fibers are located close to reinforcement fiber bundle, impregnation performance of thermoplastics is excellent [1].

The other one is low interfacial properties between the fiber and matrix. It is considered that interfacial properties in continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites can be characterized by the wetting ability and chemical interaction between fiber and matrix. Wetting ability would affect resin impregnation state during molding while chemical reaction affects composite strength. Therefore, interface design of CFRTP is very important to obtain composite materials with improved processability and mechanical performance.

In our previous research [2], it has been clarified that the CF/PP had good impregnation property but low interfacial strength in the composite performance. On the other hand, CF/MAPP had low impregnation property but high interfacial strength in the composite.

The objective of this research is to improve the both impregnation state and interfacial shear strength by using surface treatment on carbon fiber.

To achieve this objective, low molecular weight Polypropylene (L-PP) and non-ionic Polypropylene emulsifying agent (PP-emulsion) were used.

2 Fabrication Method

The materials used in this study were carbon fiber as the reinforcement (T700SC-12000 Toray Co., Ltd), and polypropylene (PP) and maleated polypropylene (MAPP) fibers as matrix resin.

To evaluate interfacial shear strength of the CF/PP or MAPP, the micro-droplet test was employed. The CF was treated by using L-PP and PP-emulsion with various concentrations at 0, 0.6, 1.4, 2.5, 3.5, and 8.0wt%.

To evaluate the impregnation state and mechanical properties of the composite, the CF/PP or MAPP composites were fabricated. A tubular braiding machine was used for fabricating MBY as an intermediate material for producing unidirectional continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites [3, 4]. CF as the reinforcement fibers untreated and treated with L-PP or PP-emulsion was aligned vertically and braided with PP or MAPP fiber to yield CF/PP or MAPP MBY by using a technique known as micro braiding. These MBYs were later used to prepare composites.

Prior to compression molding process for fabricating the composites, the MBYs were wound onto a parallel metallic frame with a size of 20×340mm equipped with a spring mechanism to prevent thermal shrinkage during molding, as shown in Fig. 2. The wound frame was then placed into a pre-heated mold with a size of 20×200mm and compression molding was performed at 200°C with a molding pressure of 10 MPa for 60 minutes. Cooling was subsequently performed by running water through the mold while keeping the specimens under constant pressure.

4 Testing Method

Micro-droplet test was performed to investigate interfacial adhesion and the interfacial shear strength of the CF/PP or MAPP interface was examined. The resin fiber was melted by using a hot plate at 220°C and a small droplet of resin was applied to a single fiber. Micro-droplet test machine HM410 (Tohei Sangyo Co.,Ltd) was used with a fiber pull-out speed of 0.03 mm/min. When the micro-droplet touches the knife edges, the interface is solicited in shear mode. The maximum load F measured before matrix detachment from the fiber is related to the fiber/matrix shear strength. The interfacial shear strength (τ) was calculated by equation 1,

$$\tau = \frac{F}{\pi dl} \quad (1)$$

where F is the maximum load, πd is the fiber circumference, and l is the embedded fiber length. The values of the fiber circumference and embedded length were characterized using microscope images as shown in Fig.3.

The wetting ability with contact angle was examined to investigate wetting ability of the CF/PP or MAPP. The resin fiber and CF filament were put on glass slide and it was melted by using a hot plate at 200°C. The resin fiber in melting was observed by using microscope as shown in Fig. 4.

The surface of specimens after micro-droplet was observed by scanning electron microscope (SEM). The specimens were dried and gold coated by using a sputtering machine (JEOL, JFC-1100E)

for 8 minutes to make the surface electrically conducting, in order to prevent accumulation of electron charges on the specimen surface during observation. The coated specimens were observed by using a scanning electron microscope (JEOL 5400).

In order to observe the impregnation state of the composite, the cross-section of CF/PP or MAPP composites were polished and observed by using an optical microscope OLYMPUS-PME3 (IC5).

For the mechanical property, 3-point bending test of unidirectional composites was performed by using an INSTRON universal testing machine (model 4206). The specimen size was 50mm in length, 15mm in width and 1.5~1.8 mm in thickness. The span length was 25mm and the test speed was 1mm/min.

5 Results and Discussion

Fig.5 shows relationship between interfacial shear strength of CF/PP or MAPP and content of surface treatment. In the case of CF/PP with L-PP, the interfacial shear strength was increased until 0.6% and then decreased with increase in the surface treatment content. While surface treatment with PP-emulsion, the interfacial shears strength was increased until 1.4% and then kept constant value with increase in the surface treatment content. In the case of CF/MAPP, the interfacial shear strength was decreased until 3.5% and then kept constant value for both L-PP and PP-emulsion. In the case of CF/PP and CF/MAPP treated with PP-emulsion, the interfacial strength was higher than that treated with L-PP.

Fig. 6 shows SEM photographs after micro-droplet test for 2.1wt%. After the micro-droplet test specimen of CF/MAPP, the breaking point of the resin had larger damage more than CF/PP. It indicated that CF/MAPP has high interfacial shear strength more than CF/PP.

Fig. 7 shows the wetting ability by contact angle of CF/PP and CF/MAPP with untreated and treated with L-PP and PP-emulsion at 2.1wt%. In the case of untreated specimens, the contact angle of CF/MAPP was bigger than that CF/PP. In the case of CF/PP treated with L-PP, the contact angle was not changed when compare with untreated

specimen but bigger than treated with PP-emulsion. While in the case of CF/MAPP treated with L-PP, the contact angle was decreased when compare with untreated specimen from 96° to 39° and still bigger than treated with PP-emulsion. In the case of CF treated with L-PP and PP-emulsion, the contact angle of CF treated with L-PP was bigger than CF treated with PP-emulsion. It indicated that the wetting ability of CF treated with L-PP was lower than CF treated with PP-emulsion.

Fig. 8 shows the impregnation state by cross-sectional photographs of composites by untreated and treated with L-PP and PP-emulsion. In the case of untreated specimens, the impregnation ratio of CF/PP was higher than CF/MAPP. In the case of CF/PP, the impregnation ratio was slightly decreased by L-PP. While in the case of CF/PP treated with PP-emulsion, impregnation ratio was 100% as same as untreated one, moreover, the fibers were highly dispersed compare with untreated one. In the case of CF/MAPP, the impregnation ratio was increased by L-PP and became 100% by PP-emulsion.

Fig.9 shows the bending strength of composites. In the case of untreated specimen, the bending strength of CF/PP was much lower than CF/MAPP. The strength of CF/PP was drastically improved by surface treatment and the increasing ratio by PP-emulsion was higher than that by L-PP. In the case of CF/MAPP, the strength was slightly improved by the surface treatment.

Fig. 10 shows the SEM photographs of surfaces of composites after bending test. In the case of CF treated by PP-emulsion, the amount of resin sit on fiber much more than CF untreated and treated by L-PP. This is an indication of strong interfacial adhesion between CF and the matrix.

From these results in the case of CF/PP, CF treated with PP-emulsion could improve the interfacial strength between fiber and resin and bending strength of composites. In the case of CF/MAPP, CF treated with PP-emulsion could improve the impregnation of the resin into fiber bundle by increasing the wetting ability and improve the bending strength of composites. It indicated that CF treated with PP-emulsion could produce composites with better mechanical performance.

6 Conclusions

The surface treatment by Low-PP and PP-emulsion was effective both for CF/PP and CF/MAPP in the impregnation properties and the interfacial properties for CF/PP composites. It was established that surface treatment by Low-PP and PP-emulsion could produce composites with better mechanical properties for CF/PP and CF/MAPP.

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Fig. 1 Fabrication of Micro-braided yarn (MBY)

Fig. 2 Fabrication method of unidirectional specimens

Fig. 3 Micro-droplet test

Fig. 4 Wetting ability by contact angle test

Fig. 5 Relationship between interfacial shear strength of CF/PP or MAPP and surface treatment content.

Fig. 6 SEM photographs of micro-droplet test

Fig. 7 Photographs of contact angle

Fig. 8 Cross sectional photographs of composites.

Fig. 9 Bending strength of composites

CF/PP

CF/MAPP

Fig. 10 SEM photographs of surfaces of composites